

What is your gender? () Male () Female () Other: _____

() Prefer not to say

What is your age?

What is your education level?

- () None
- () Pre-school/Kindergarten
- () Elementary School I
- () Middle School (Elementary School II)
- () High School
- () Higher Education (Undergraduate)
- () Postgraduate
- () Master's Degree
- () Doctorate

How often do you use the internet? () Daily () Weekly () Monthly () Rarely () Never

Do you own a smartphone, tablet, or computer? () Yes () No

How often do you use these devices? () Daily () Weekly () Monthly () Rarely () Never

Do you usually perform bank transactions using your cell phone? () Yes () No

If not, why?

- () I prefer to perform transactions in person at banks or lottery houses
- () I find the bank application very difficult or complicated to use
- () I do not trust the security of online transactions
- () I do not have anyone to teach me how to use the application
- () My cell phone or internet connection is not suitable for this
- () Other: _____

How often do you use banking services on your cell phone? () Daily () Weekly ()

Monthly () Rarely () Never

Which online bank do you use (show support material)?

How long have you been using internet banking services?

- () Less than 1 year
- () 1–2 years
- () 3–5 years
- () More than 5 years

How did you learn to use the bank on your cell phone?

- () By myself
- () Help from friends/family
- () Courses
- () Other: _____

Do you find it easy or difficult to use internet banking services?

- Very easy
- Easy
- Neither easy nor difficult
- Difficult
- Very difficult

Why?

What are the main challenges you face when using the bank online?

What bank activities do you perform online? Transfers Bill payment Balance inquiry Other: _____

What do you find most useful about online banking?

Is there anything you would like to be added or improved?

Do you feel the lack of any type of help when using the bank online? (Yes/No) What type of help?

Do you feel secure performing online bank transactions?

- Very secure
- Secure
- Neither secure nor insecure
- Insecure
- Very insecure

Why?

What do you do to feel secure when using the bank online?

Do you find the bank's app screen or website easy to understand and use? (Yes/No) Why?

Is there anything on the screen (buttons, menus, colors) that you find confusing or difficult to use? (Yes/No) What?

Do you have suggestions on how the screen could be improved to facilitate use? (e.g., increase font size, simplify menus)?

Have you ever needed help resolving an issue with online banking? (Yes/No) How was that experience?

If you could change anything about online banking, what would it be?

Comments/suggestions on how to improve services for older adults:

If you find the bank app difficult to use, what are the difficulties?

- Confusing interface
- Small letters and buttons
- Fear of making errors
- I don't know how to start
- Other: _____

What would make you feel more secure using the bank app?

- More information about security
- Available technical support
- Bank guarantees
- Other: _____

If you don't have anyone to teach you how to use the app, what could help?

- In-person courses offered by the bank
- Video tutorials
- Help from family/friends
- Other: _____

Improvements that would facilitate app use:

- Clearer and simpler instructions
- Increased size of letters/buttons
- More intuitive interface
- Step-by-step virtual assistant
- Other: _____

Would a dedicated section for older adults increase your confidence in the app?

Yes No

What else could encourage you to use the bank app?

- Positive recommendations from other older adults
- Practical demonstrations in public places
- Other: _____

If you stopped using the app, why?

- Technical difficulties
- Confusing app, too much information
- Lack of confidence
- I don't know how to start
- Fear of making errors
- I don't know how to correct errors
- Lack of bank reassurance/proof
- Confusing functionalities
- I prefer in-person service
- Other: _____